

FERTILE VARIETIES OF GOOSEBERRIES

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Annotation: This article provides information about the productive, productive varieties of the goose plant and their types ,which have become important in agriculture not only in Uzbekistan, but throughout the world.

Keywords: Bukhara light-6,Hurley Gulistan,ISTIKLOL - 14th grade,Andijan light-35,NAMANGAN - 34th grade,sort of luck,SURHAN - 103, Khorezm -127, Cotton (lot. Gossypium) - Malvaceae thermophilic, Microneura, fiber.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о продуктивных, малопродуктивных сортах гусяного растения и их видах, которые стали важными в сельском хозяйстве не только Узбекистана, но и всего мира.

Ключевые слова: Бухарский лайт-6,Херли Гулистан,ИСТИКЛОЛ - 14 сорт,Андижанский лайт-35,НАМАНГАНСКИЙ – 34 сорт,сорт удачи,СУРГАН - 103, Хорезм -127, Хлопок (лот. Gossypium) - Мальвовые теплолюбивые, микронеуральные, волокнистые.

Cotton (lot. Gossypium) is a species of the malvaceae family.Cotton is a thermophilic plant. It grows on all kinds of soils, in the sentence, on icy, swampy, sandy, rocky, Meadow-swampy soils, the surface of which until recently was covered with water.Cotton growing in many countries is the leading network of rural areas. Cotton is grown in 84 countries around the world. The highest indicator for the production of cotton fiber is China-6.929 million tons. After them: India – 6,634 million.T., US-2,811 million.t., Pakistan-2,076 million.t., Brazil-1,705 million.t. In our mamlaktim, the purpose of ensuring self-food security in subsequent years, solving employment problems in villages, supporting diversified farms, cotton planting areas have been reduced several times. Although part of the additional fields was allocated for grain, fruit and vegetable crops, attention to Cotton did not decrease, on the contrary, with the use of Science and new technologies, the task was set to replace the bare type of cotton, to improve the yield of cotton. crop rotation system, increase labor productivity and cotton productivity. 36 varieties of gooseberries are grown in the turlichodes of our country.The STEM is strong, does not settle, the leaves are moderately pubescent. The boxes are medium, oval, the seeds are medium dark, gray. Fiber axis, the rolling period is 120-125 days.The weight of the goose in a box is 6.2 g.The fiber length is 34-35 mm, the tensile strength is 28.6 g.k.teks, hardness 4,9-5,0. g. k., metric number 5880-5950, fiber output 36.8-37.2%. Micronutrients 4.8-4.9, weight of 1000 pieces of seeds 119-125 g.Fiber belongs to the industrial type. Created in koyer: Andijan branch of the Research Institute of agricultural technologies of selection, seed production and cotton growing.included in the State Register

ingen. 2006 year.Extra-budgetary pension fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

BUKHARA LIGHT-6

The growing season is 120-127 days.The weight of cotton in one box is 5.9 - 7.5 g.Fiber length-35.0-36.0 mm.Fiber yield-35.5-36.5%.Fiber softness-6000-6200 fiber hardness 4.5-4.6 gc.Micronutrients-4,2-4,6.Fiber Type-IV.Productivity-40.0-50.0 kg / ha.Created in Uzbekistan: Uzbekistan author: A. Batalov was included in the state register in 1990.It is recommended to stay in Bukhara, Kashkadarya and Navoi regions of our country.

HURLEY GULISTAN

Plant growth 100-120 CM.The stems and branches are medium hairy. The weight of 1000 seeds is 128-132 g,the weight of cotton in a box is 6.6-7.0 g.The average growing season of the variety: 122-125 days in the northern regions, 115-118 days in the south, in these regions it is considered medium-ripe.Fiber IV belongs to the stable, the tensile strength of the fiber is32, 5-33, 4 gs/teks.Fiber output 37.5-38.0%, fiber length 35-36 mm.Microneura 4.1-4.4, fiber length (UHI) 1.22-1.24 inches.Outside in koyer: former O ' PA cotton and seed chilik Research Institute.Included in the State Register in 2020.Recommended for growing in the Syrdarya region of our country.

ISTIKLOL-GRADE 14

The period from the appearance of shoots to the opening of the box is 110-120 days. The STEM is strong, does not lie down. A box with a theft of 6.0-6.4 g has a pocket uvali, a blue flute, mostly 5 pieces, which open freely when ripe, the cotton does not fall off.Industrial fiber IV type, fiber color axis, flour 37-38%, length 34-35 mm, fiber hardness 4.4 gf, softness 6100-6400 m.The average length is 1.20 inches. The weight of 1000 seeds is 110-115 g.dense gray has hairs. The average yield of the variety is 36-42 G / ha.Published in koyer: Research Institute of cotton growing and seed growing.Authors: S. Rahmonqulov, Sh.Namazov, A. Omonturdiev and others.Included in the state register in 2016.Recommended for planting in the Andijan region of our country.

ANDIJAN NURI-35

The STEM is strong, does not settle, the leaves are moderately pubescent. The boxes are medium, oval, the seeds are medium dark, gray. Fiber bullet, the reading period is 120-125 days. The weight of cotton is 6.2 g. Fiber length 34-35 mm, tear 28.6 g.k.teks, rigidity 4.9-5.0 g.k., metric number 5880-5950, fiber unit 36.8-37.2%. Micronutrients 4.8-4.9, the weight of seeds of 1000 pieces is 119-125 g. fiber industry includes type V. Established joy: Andijan branch of the Research Institute of cotton selection, seed production and Agrotechnology. Included in the state register in 2006. Extra-budgetary pension fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan

NAMANGAN-CLASS 34

The Cotta of the bushes is conical, 100-110 CM in height. The weight of 1000 seeds is 112-117 g, the oscillator is yellow. The growth of the goose in one bag is 4.7-5.6 g. The period from germination to the opening of the first box: 116-120 days in the middle and Northern Districts, 108-114 days in the southern districts, which is calculated in the early period. These are the regions. Fiber IV belongs to the stable, the staple length of the fiber is 33.0-35.0 mm, the tensile strength is 27.6 gk/teks, the tensile density is 178 m/teks. Fiber output 37,4-39,0%. Micronutral indices 4.1-4.4. Fiber is popular in the world market. External in koyer: "red-Rovot" experimental farm of the PA Research Institute of cotton and horticulture. Authors: V. Avtonomov, Sh. Namazov and others. Included in the state register in 2009. Extra-budgetary pension fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Sort luck

Early variety. The growing season is 105-115 days. The bowl is large, 4-5 pieces, with an egg-shaped nose, (6.0-7.0 g), the goose did not fall out of the bowl. Fiber productivity 35.0-36.0%, length 35.0-36.0 mm, hardness 4.5 GK, microneedle index 4.4-4.6. Urugi is large, slave. The weight of 1000 seeds is 130-135 g, the width is 19-20%. Place of establishment: Cotton selection and Research Institute of the Ministry of Agriculture and water resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Authors: Kim R. G., Amanturdiyev A. B. and others. Included in the state register in 1999. Samarkand and Khorezm regions, Republic of Karakalpakstan

SARALAB SURKHAN-103

Turning advantages: high solubility, yield and high quality fiber. The harvest is high thanks to the photo step by October 1 the harvest is fully weeping. Endure Fusarium, garmsil and water tankism in the soil. Due to the compactness of the company, it is recommended to increase the number of games and add them in an additional way. The machine is adapted for assembly. Externalized location: Research Institute of cotton growing, seed growing and Agrotechnology. Authors: Kimsanbaev A., Avtonomov V. A. Sh. Namazav.E., Kazanov X. and others. Included in the state register for 2020. Recommended for growing in surkhandarya region.

Khorezm variety-127

Medium fiber. The morphological structure has many stems erect, 90-120 CM, the STEM is covered with medium green hairs. Cotton in one box is on average 6.0-6.5 g. The Oval is more rounded, pasty, smooth, hairy, judaham opens well. The weight of 1000 pieces of urug is 122-132 g, the oiliness is 24.5%. Fiber output 36.5-38.4%, fiber length 34.5-36.0 mm, metric number 6100 (164), tension strength 4.4-4.6 GK, fiber length 34.5-36.0 mm, relativity strength 26.0-27.3 GK/Tex, Micron.

Place of establishment: Khorezm branch of the Cotton Research Institute of Uzbekistan was included in the state register in 2002. Congratulations on the election of President of the

Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov as president of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the Oqsaray residence.

Conclusion:

This article provides information about the productive, productive varieties of the goose plant and their types, which have become important in agriculture not only in Uzbekistan, but throughout the world. In conclusion, we can say that because there is a lot of work to be done in the field of selection. We have to work hard in this area.

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